

**AN IMPORTANT LEGAL BASIS CREATED FOR THE INTRODUCTION
OF THE INSTITUTION OF PRELIMINARY HEARING IN
ADMINISTRATIVE COURTS**

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses the legal document adopted for the introduction of the preliminary hearing institution, the importance and place of this document in the practice of administrative courts.

Also, the general aspects of the application of the original institution in foreign countries and some important cases in judicial practice are highlighted, foreign and national legislation are comparatively studied and information is included about the urgency of introducing this institution in our judicial practice.

Key words: legal document, preliminary hearing, active participation of the court, international standards, judicial practice

In recent years, attention to the legal system in our country has paid off, many reforms aimed at ensuring and protecting human rights and freedoms, their legal interests have been carried out in our country.

In this regard, the decision No. 33 "On additional measures to introduce modern mechanisms for the protection of the rights of citizens and business entities through the courts" adopted by the head of our state on 30.01.2025 as part of the reforms being carried out in the field of administrative court has become of special

importance¹. As we get acquainted with this decision, we are more confident that legally specific tasks have been defined in order to further improve the activity of administrative courts. That is, with this legal document, administrative court proceedings are carried out on the basis of the principle of "active participation of the court", in which administrative courts are given the obligation to collect evidence on their own initiative to determine the true circumstances of the case, and special attention is paid to creating conditions for the citizen or business entity whose rights have been violated to participate in the collection of evidence only to the extent of their ability. At this point, if we think about the principle of active participation of the court, before giving an understanding of this principle, we found it necessary to pay attention to the view of jurist Yu. Starilov, in which he stated that the specific nature of the disputes that arose between the subjects of administrative-legal relations can be expressed by the inequality of the parties, that is, one of the parties will have the authority of power and management². In judicial practice, there are indeed many such cases, therefore this principle is very important for ensuring the legal protection of a person in administrative court proceedings.

Usually, this principle is defined as follows: the conduct of administrative court cases is carried out on the basis of the active participation of the court, the explanations, applications, petitions of the persons participating in the court case, the evidence presented by them and investigates comprehensively, fully and impartially all factual circumstances relevant to the proper resolution of the administrative case without being limited to other materials of the case.

The court collects additional evidence on its own initiative or at the request of

¹Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 30, 2025 PQ-33 /On additional measures to introduce modern mechanisms for the protection of the rights of citizens and business entities through the courts <https://www.lex.uz/uz/docs/-7350794>

² Yu.N. Starilov. Administrative justice: Theory of problems-1998,

persons participating in the case, as well as performs other actions aimed at solving the tasks of administrative court proceedings. People participating in the case must assist the court in investigating the true circumstances of the case and gathering evidence. The need for the active participation of the court in the resolution of administrative disputes is not only the real inequality of the parties' opportunities, but also the lack of funds or opportunities to determine the important circumstances of the case, objective intervention, it is also associated with the risk of misunderstandings between the administrative body and the individual. It is this principle that is directly related to the actions that the judge can take during the preliminary hearing, when the judge communicates with the parties during the preliminary hearing, explaining to the parties what rights and obligations they have and the elements of this principle are evident in the explanation of obligations and in appropriate actions related to the appointment of an expert witness or the involvement of a witness.

Also, in paragraph b of the fifth part of this decision, special instructions are given on the introduction of the preliminary hearing institution in the operation of the administrative court, according to which:

- the preliminary hearing in the course of administrative court proceedings is held in the cases provided for by law;
- at the preliminary hearing, the applicant's demands and the defendant's objections are clarified, measures are taken to eliminate the deficiencies in the application;
- explanations will be given to the applicant to provide the necessary evidence and the respondent's opinion in writing to prove the requirements;
- the judge will give a preliminary legal assessment of the claims in the application and the evidence in the case (clarification of claims, replacement of parties not involved in the case, involvement of an additional defendant, etc.).

It is not allowed to express a final opinion on the substantive resolution of the case under consideration;

According to the information given above, this decision is made by administrative courts making a radical turn in its activities, it attaches special importance to the further improvement of court cases and the administration of justice and the provision of human rights. Along with large-scale reforms carried out in our country, it is also important to adapt the judicial system to international standards. If we pay attention to the international judicial systems, the institution of "Preliminary hearing" has been introduced in the administrative courts of many countries. In particular, the introduction of the preliminary hearing in Germany is connected with the establishment of the administrative court, which dates back to the second half of the 19th century, and the preliminary hearing in the courts of this country is mainly conducted to protect and ensure human rights.

In the Russian Federation, although there are no separate specialized administrative courts, there are courts of general jurisdiction and arbitration (arbitration) courts dealing with administrative cases also, the working procedure of this institution is widely covered in the Administrative Procedure Code of Russia. We can cite information similar to the above from the activities of administrative courts in many countries, for example, Armenia, Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan. Including, when we study these countries, the main purpose of conducting a preliminary hearing in administrative courts is to fully prepare the case for trial, to clarify the demands of the parties, to verify their relevance to the case, to eliminate obstacles that may arise when the court considers the case, to explain the rights and obligations of the parties, if there is a procedural violation, it is to eliminate them and, if possible, to ensure a timely and fair resolution of the dispute by reconciling the parties, and the introduction of this institution has been effective in ensuring justice for several years.

The institution of preliminary hearing is widely used in international judicial practice as a means of quick, economical and effective dispute resolution. This institution is important in determining the nature of disputes brought to court at the

initial stage, clarifying the positions of the parties and regulating the process. The experience of foreign countries shows that a preliminary hearing saves time and resources in resolving disputes.

One of the unique aspects of this institution is that the parties understand their position and proceed to further proceedings of the court based on their circumstances and capabilities. For example, they will have clear information about whether the evidence presented is sufficient or not, whether there is an additional objection on the other side or not. After studying these circumstances, the judge will have a preliminary opinion on the case and will try to eliminate procedural errors and shortcomings in the case, which substantive legal norms should be paid attention to when conducting the case.

In a word, the development of the judicial system in accordance with international standards and the implementation of such measures in the field will ensure that the activities of state bodies are conducted on a legal basis, the rights and interests of citizens and legal entities will be effectively protected, the administrative court will be improved taking into account international standards, openness in the field and transparency, most importantly, serves to turn administrative courts into real people's courts. For this reason, the issue of conducting relevant research and introducing it to our administrative courts, having studied this institution in depth, has shown its relevance. The introduction of this institution in Uzbekistan has an important role not only in improving the judicial system, but also in strengthening the trust of citizens in the judicial system.

List of used literature:

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